

REPLICA MOLDING OF LIQUID CRYSTAL POLYMER MICROSTRUCTURES FOR ACTIVE SURFACES

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Keywords: *polymer, liquid crystal, microstructure, molding, actuator*

1. Introduction

Surfaces with dynamic micro- and nanoscale textures can potentially be used to manipulate friction drag, optical reflection, thermal transport, and other properties. However, in order to realize these applications, surfaces must be made consistently over large areas, and integrated with existing laminate and skin materials for use in vehicles such as aircraft.

Liquid crystal polymers are interesting candidate materials for active surfaces due to their tunable mechanical properties [1-3], anisotropic expansion upon heating [4], and opportunity for optically directed actuation [5-7]. For example, thin sheets made from stiff glassy liquid crystal network (LCN) polymers have been shown to oscillate at 30Hz with a tip displacement amplitude of 170° [8]. However, to our knowledge, miniaturization of LCN actuators in the form of surface-bound micropillars has not been demonstrated.

We present a replica molding (RM) fabrication technique [9] to obtain high fidelity surface bound glassy LCN microstructure actuators over large areas. The removal of oxygen during curing was critical to achieve high-fidelity replicas with smooth surface texture, while the necessary LCN alignment for actuation was obtained via curing in a magnetic field. Cast microstructures had lateral dimensions of a few microns and aspect ratios (AR) up to 15:1. A gradient based edge detection algorithm [10] was used to quantify the LCN microstructure actuation, verifying anisotropy of the network.

2. Fabrication

LCN microstructure arrays were fabricated by replica molding within a magnetic field in a

controlled atmosphere. The experimental setup includes a custom magnetic circuit designed to straighten and confine a magnetic through the sample. The magnetic yoke was placed inside a vacuum jar, whose aluminum base was in contact with a hotplate and is shown in Fig. 1a. A green LED light source, used for cross-linking, was located outside of the vacuum jar.

A LC powder mixture composed of 20 wt% optically active 4,40-bis[6-(acryloxy)hexyloxy] azobenzene monomers (A6Z6 from BEAM Co.), 78 wt % thermally active RMM491 monomer mixture (EMD Millipore), and 2 wt % I-784 photoinitiator (Ciba) was created [1]. The constituents of the RMM491 mixture and the optically active LC monomer, labeled A6Z6, are shown in Fig. 1b.

Master templates can be fabricated using standard silicon dry etching processes, or alternatively CNT/SU-8 composite microstructures may be used to fabricate complex 3D geometries [9]. From the master, a polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) negative was cast and used to create the LCN replicas. PDMS was vacuum cast over the deep reactive ion etch (DRIE) patterned silicon master and cured at 120°C for 20min to form the negative mold (Fig. 1c). The powder mixture was added to the negative and heated to 110°C for 10 min at a pressure below 1 Torr (Fig. 1d). The magnetic field (0.3T) applied by the fixture causes benzene containing LC monomers to align in a cooperative fashion along it. The cooperative alignment of benzene rings inside a magnetic field was first suggested by de Gennes [11] and successfully demonstrated for use in liquid crystal polymers by Buguin et al. [4] The mixture was cooled to 75°C at 1°C/min resulting in a LC in the nematic phase with its director aligned along the magnetic field. Placing the sample in a strong magnetic field, which has

Fig. 1. (a) Experimental setup used to cast LCN microstructures. (b) Casting of the PDMS negative from the DRIE etched silicon master. (c) Close up of molten LC mixture inside the magnetic field. (d) Manual demolding of replicated structures. (e) Diagrams of the monomers used in the LCN mixture. (f) Schematic of custom microscope schematic used during testing.

been straightened via a magnetic yoke, and cooling it slowly achieves the necessary order and alignment for actuation. The sample was then exposed to green light (540 nm wavelength) for 40 min, which initiates cross-linking of the ordered LC monomers into a polymer network. After cooling to room temperature the LCN replica was manually demolded from the soft PDMS negative (Fig 1e).

A custom-built microscope was used to image the microstructures during actuation (Fig. 1f). This microscope has both a linearly polarized blue light and a white light source. During actuation the samples were exposed to linearly polarized blue light (~440 nm wavelength) aligned parallel to the LC director for 3-5 minutes. After actuation the sample was exposed to visible light for 15 minutes or heated to 90°C causing it to relax and recover its original shape. Azobenzene moieties predominantly take on the *trans* isomerization during the relaxation and the polymer network recovers its initial higher order nematic phase.

3. Results

We found that removal of oxygen was crucial for achieving high fidelity LCN replicas with low surface roughness. Samples cast without degassing have large voids due to air bubbles trapped in the molten powder mixture and have very large surface roughness (Fig. 2a). Fig. 2b shows a sample that was vacuum cast at 1 Torr to remove air bubbles from the molten powder mixture, after which air was reintroduced during curing. The bottom part of the SEM image shows the sample edge that was exposed to the air. Microstructures closer to the exposed edge have significantly larger surface roughness, suggesting that oxygen exposure impacts the crystallization of the LCN. We found that samples with large surface roughness have significantly reduced photogenerated strains.

Using these findings to drive process improvements, we show (Fig. 3) cast microstructures with a variety of sizes and shapes, with both small and large aspect ratios. Large microstructures with different cross-section shapes are shown in Fig. 3a, while large arrays of high aspect ratio (AR, height:width) structures are shown in Fig. 3b. The semi-cylindrical micropillars are 55 μm tall and have an AR of approximately 15:1.

Fig. 2. (a) LCN replicas cast without degassing of the molten LC mixture. (b) Degassed replica that was exposed to air during curing with close up images of selected regions, showing increased surface roughness in the presence of oxygen.

The LCN micropillars can be actuated by polarized blue light capable of providing sufficient energy to drive both the trans-cis and the cis-trans isomerization (Fig. 4a), due to an overlap between the cis and trans isomer absorption spectra [12]. The azobenzene trans isomer moieties absorb

significantly less polarized light if they are oriented perpendicular the polarization, gradually creating a statistical buildup of such isomers. This buildup disturbs the nematic phase, reducing its order and achieving a volumetric shape change (Fig. 4b). This

Fig. 3. (a) Heterogeneous low aspect ratio optically active LCN microstructures. (b) High yield, large area array of asymmetric microstructures. Inset shows close up image of microstructure.

shape change can be used to alter either the height of a micropillar if the director is oriented along its axis (Fig. 4c) or the pillar cross section if the director is oriented perpendicular to it. Because the actuation is based on the disruption of the nematic LC phase, having good alignment prior to cross-linking the LC monomers is crucial. A comparison between similar LCN compositions and other actuating materials is shown in Fig. 4d [13]. Although the maximum generated stress of LCN materials are lower than that of other comparable polymers, we show that LCN materials can be cast into a verity of useful microstructures.

An interpolation-based edge tracking algorithm [14] was implemented to resolve sub-pixel actuation of cast LCN micropillars, imaged using the microscope described above.

Fig. 4. (a) *trans-cis-trans* isomerization of azobenzene due to polarized blue light exposure. (b) Schematic of nematic and isotropic LCN phase containing thermally active (purple) and optically active LC molecules (orange). (c) Volumetric shape change due to LCN phase change. (d) Maximum stress and strain generated by comparable actuating materials [13].

Fig. 5. (a) SEM image of optically active LCN micro-pillar. (b) Sample optical image of the top-down view from a custom microscope used in for edge tracking. Arrows indicate strain direction. (c) Results of gradient based edge tracking algorithm, showing edge movement [ref].

A SEM image and a top-down optical image of the optically active LCN microstructure are shown in Fig. 5a and 5b, respectively. We measured a photogenerated strain of 0.25% orthogonal to the LCN director and a 0.11% contraction along it after 5 min of exposure to linearly polarized blue light oriented perpendicular to the LC director (Fig. 5c). The contraction along the director occurs because the rod-like stiff LC moieties gradually rotate away from it. Samples cured without the magnetic field showed no actuation. Previous studies with similar LCN compositions have measured a photogenerated strain along the director of 0.15% and a stiffness of 1.8 GPa using dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA) [15]. We expect that larger strains could be achieved via use of UV light, by achieving improved LCN alignment during the replica molding process, by composition reformulation at the expense of reduced stiffness [1], and by physical aging of the material [16].

4. Conclusion

We have fabricated and tested LCN microactuators, exhibiting up to 0.25% strain along the director and a 0.11% contraction orthogonal to it after 5 min exposure of polarized blue light. For the first time, centimeter-scale areas of high aspect ratio microstructures were fabricated, enabled by careful environmental process control and removal of oxygen during casting. With further characterization and improvement of the optically-induced strain, this technology would be suitable for fabrication of active surface textures, such as for use in microfluidics, and possibly on the surfaces of miniature vehicles.

5. Acknowledgements

Financial support was provided by the Air Force Office of Scientific Research (YIP Award FA9550-11-1-0089, program manager Dr. B.L. "Les" Lee). Microfabrication was performed at the Lurie Nanofabrication Facility (LNF), while electron microscopy was performed at the Michigan Electron Microbeam Analysis Laboratory (EMAL). We thank Dr. Timothy White (AFRL) for helpful insights, discussions, and provided materials. We also thank Ryan Oliver for contributions to the design and fabrication of the test apparatus.

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